

PAIRWISE LIKELIHOOD PROCEDURE FOR TWO-SAMPLE LOCATION PROBLEM

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ABSTRACT. This paper is about estimating shift parameter by using pairwise differences in the two-sample location problem, which assumes $G(x)=F(x-\Delta)$. The parameter Δ is called location *shift parameter* between populations of $F(x)$ and $G(x)$. Distribution and density functions of the pairwise differences can be found and used to construct a log likelihood function with respect to the shift parameter. An estimator of the shift parameter is found by Newton's one step algorithm from the log likelihood function. Asymptotic properties of the new estimator which is similar to a regular MLE estimator are shown under some regularity conditions. As an example, normal and Laplace Distribution model assumptions are investigated using the proposed approach. Moreover, a hypothesis testing procedure is developed and shown that pairwise difference approach is asymptotically equivalent to the Rao's score type likelihood test.

1. INTRODUCTION

Let X_1, \dots, X_{n_1} and Y_1, \dots, Y_{n_2} be two independent i.i.d samples from continuous distribution functions $F(x)$ and $G(x)$, respectively. We assume a relationship of $G(x)=F(x-\Delta)$ where Δ is a location *shift parameter* between $F(x)$ and $G(x)$. Therefore, we will consider a location shift model and focus our attention to estimate of the shift parameter of Δ . A hypothesis testing for this model could be defined by,

$$H_0 : \Delta = \Delta_0 \text{ vs } H_a : \Delta \neq \Delta_0$$

If $\Delta_0 = 0$, the hypothesis test becomes:

$$H_0 : F(x) = G(x) \text{ vs } H_a : F(x) \neq G(x)$$

which is very common in two sample location problem.

The problem of estimating the shift parameter Δ_0 has been studied extensively in the past. It can be shown that the classic least squares method (minimizing the L_2 norm) leads to $\hat{\Delta}_{LS} = \bar{Y} - \bar{X}$. It has been shown by Hettmansperger-McKean [3] that

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\Delta}_{LS} - \Delta_0) \rightarrow N(0, \sigma^2 \frac{1}{\lambda(1-\lambda)})$$

where σ^2 is the common variance of the population distributions, $G(x)$ and $F(x)$, and $n_1/n \rightarrow \lambda$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Hodges-Lehmann [4], showed that the shift parameter estimator based on Wilcoxon ranks is given by

$$\hat{\Delta}_R = \text{med}_{i,j}\{Y_j - X_i\}$$

which is the median of the pairwise differences. Hodges-Lehmann [4] also showed that

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\Delta}_R - \Delta_0) \rightarrow N(0, \tau^2 \frac{1}{\lambda(1-\lambda)})$$

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FIGURE 1. Illustration of Two Sample Location Problem

where the scale parameter $\tau = [\sqrt{12} \int f^2(x)dx]^{-1}$ and $n_1/n \rightarrow \lambda$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Anderson and Hettmansberger [1] showed that

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\Delta}_G - \Delta_0) \rightarrow N\left(0, \frac{\delta^2 E[\tau^2(x)]}{[E\tau'(x)]^2} \frac{1}{\lambda(1-\lambda)}\right),$$

where δ is the scale parameter, $\tau(t) = \int \psi((t-u)/\delta)f(u)du$ and τ' is the derivative of τ . Tasdan-Sievers [6] proposed a smoothed Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon approach to find an estimator for Δ . They showed that

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\Delta}_s - \Delta_0) \rightarrow N\left(0, \frac{1}{c^2}\right)$$

and the efficacy $c = \mu'(0)/\sigma(0)$, where

$$\mu'(0) = \int \int l(y-x)dF(x)dF(y) \text{ and } \sigma(0) = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{\lambda(1-\lambda)}}.$$

In Section 2, we will introduce the main idea of the study. It will be shown that by using pairwise differences, a likelihood function can be constructed and solved to estimate the shift parameter. In addition, a test procedure will be developed to test the hypothesis defined above. In Section 3, the properties of the estimator such as asymptotic normality will be shown. Another theorem proves that the proposed method is an equivalent of Rao's score type test. In Section 4, example of several models will be applied to the proposed solutions. The paper ends with a conclusion in Section 5.

2. PROPOSED PROCEDURE

The main idea behind the proposed procedure is to find the distribution function of the pairwise differences. First, consider that we $F(x)=G(x)$, which assumes no shift model. Let $Z_{ij} = Y_j - X_i$ for all i and j differences and $H(z) = P(Y_j - X_i \leq z)$.

We define

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(Z_{ij} < z) &= P(Y_j - X_i < z) \\
 &= \int P(Y_j - X_i \leq z | X_i = x) dF(x) \\
 &= \int P(Y_j \leq z + x) dF(x) \\
 (2.1) \quad H(z) &= \int G(x + z) dF(x)
 \end{aligned}$$

The resulting $H(z)$ is the distribution function (CDF) of the $Z_{ij} = Y_j - X_i$ pairwise differences. Now consider that $F(x - \Delta) = G(x)$, which assumes a shift in the model. Then, we will have

$$\begin{aligned}
 H(z) &= \int G(x + z) dF(x) \\
 (2.2) \quad H_{\Delta}(z) &= \int F(x + z - \Delta) dF(x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Next, by assuming that it exists, the probability density function $h_{\Delta}(z)$, can be found by

$$(2.3) \quad h(z, \Delta) = \frac{dH(z)}{dz} = \int f(x + z - \Delta) f(x) dx$$

The result is like a convolution operation that convolutes two functions. Let $h_{\Delta}(z) = u(z - \Delta)$. Therefore, we can consider the problem as a location parameter problem. The log-likelihood function of the pairwise differences of the data by using $u(z - \Delta)$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
 L(\Delta) &= \prod_i \prod_j u(y_j - x_i - \Delta) \\
 l(\Delta) &= \log[L(\Delta)] = \sum_i \sum_j \log[u(y_j - x_i - \Delta)] \\
 (2.4) \quad l'(\Delta) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta} \log[L(\Delta)] = - \sum_i \sum_j \frac{u'(y_j - x_i - \Delta)}{u(y_j - x_i - \Delta)}
 \end{aligned}$$

To estimate Δ parameter, $l'(\Delta)$ will be set to zero and solved for Δ . $l'(\Delta)$ can be considered a score function which determines the estimating equations for the MLE estimator of Δ . However, there might be no root or there might be more than one root. In that case, a maximizing value of the estimator should be taken as MLE estimator. Theorem 6.1.1 from Hogg-McKean-Craig [2] states that asymptotically the likelihood function is maximized at true value Δ_0 of the parameter. Therefore, it is appropriate to take the value that maximizes the likelihood function for more than one root cases. Still it could be difficult or impossible to find an explicit formula for some estimators but a solution can be found by a numerical approximation method. One of the iterative methods that could be used is the Newton's one-step estimator which requires that the initial value must be a consistent estimator. Newton's iteration starts with an initial estimate of Δ . Let $\tilde{\Delta}$ be the initial value

and a consistent estimator of Δ , then set

$$(2.5) \quad \widehat{\Delta} = \widetilde{\Delta} - \frac{l'(\widetilde{\Delta})}{l''(\widetilde{\Delta})}$$

The result is the one step estimator of Δ . An algorithm will be provided for the proposed estimator in the appendix section. In addition, R program has "uniroot" function available for this type of problem. The resulting estimator, we call $\widehat{\Delta}$, is the Maximum Likelihood Estimator (MLE) of the true shift parameter based on the pairwise difference. An example of the proposed solution will be given in section 4.

3. PROPERTIES OF PROPOSED SOLUTION

One of the advantages of using pairwise differences is that it can be treated as one sample location parameter problem. A score type likelihood test can be developed so that there is no need for an estimate of Δ . In the next two theorems, we show that under same regularity conditions, the proposed estimator is consistent and has an asymptotic distribution of $\widehat{\Delta}$. First, we will show that the proposed estimator is consistent by Theorem 3.1. Before that we need to make some assumptions (regularity conditions). These assumptions are similar to the regular maximum likelihood assumptions.

Assumptions(Regularity Conditions):

- (A1) $h(z, \Delta)$ is a distinct pdf; i.e $\Delta \neq \Delta' \Rightarrow h(z, \Delta) \neq h(z, \Delta')$.
- (A2) $h(z, \Delta)$ have common support for all $\Delta \in \Omega$.
- (A3) The point Δ_0 is an interior point in Ω .
- (A4) $h(z, \Delta)$ is three times differentiable as a function of Δ .
- (A5) The integral $\int h(z, \Delta)dz$ can be differentiated twice under the integral sign a function of Δ .

Theorem 3.1. *Suppose that the regularity conditions A1-A2 hold and $h(z, \Delta)$ is differentiable with respect to Δ in Ω . Then, with probability approaching 1 as $n \rightarrow \infty$, there exist $\widehat{\Delta}$ such that $l'(\widehat{\Delta}) = 0$ and $\widehat{\Delta} \xrightarrow{P} \Delta_0$.*

Above theorem can be proven by Theorem 6.1.3 from Hogg-McKean-Craig [2]. Therefore, the proof will not be discussed here. By the following theorem, we show that the proposed estimator is asymptotically normal as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Theorem 3.2. *Assume that the regularity conditions and Theorem 3.1 hold. Also assume that the Fisher information satisfies $0 < I(\Delta_0) < \infty$. Finally, assume that $l(\Delta)$ has three derivatives in a neighborhood of Δ_0 and $l'''(\delta)$ is uniformly bounded in this neighborhood. Then, we have*

$$\sqrt{n}(\widehat{\Delta} - \Delta_0) \xrightarrow{D} N(0, \frac{1}{I(\Delta_0)})$$

Proof. The proof is a typical MLE proof that can be found in Serfling [5] or Hogg-McKean-Craig [2]. By using second order Taylor expansion of $l'(\Delta)$ at Δ_0 and evaluating $l'(\Delta)$ at $\widehat{\Delta}$, we get

$$l'(\widehat{\Delta}) = l'(\Delta_0) + (\widehat{\Delta} - \Delta_0)l''(\Delta_0) + \frac{1}{2}(\widehat{\Delta} - \Delta_0)^2l'''(\Delta^*)$$

where Δ^* is between $\widehat{\Delta}$ and Δ_0 . Since $l'(\widehat{\Delta}) = 0$, we can rearrange the last equation as

$$\sqrt{n}(\widehat{\Delta} - \Delta_0) = \frac{\sqrt{n}l'(\Delta_0)}{-n^{-1}l''(\Delta_0) - (2n)^{-1}(\widehat{\Delta} - \Delta_0)l'''(\Delta^*)}$$

By the Central Limit Theorem and Law of Large Numbers,

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}l'(\Delta_0) \xrightarrow{D} N[0, I(\Delta_0)]$$

and

$$-n^{-1}l''(\Delta_0) \xrightarrow{P} I(\Delta_0)$$

where $I(\Delta_0) = V[\frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta} \log u(Y - X - \Delta_0)]$. We will assume that the second term in the denominator of the expression goes to zero as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and $n^{-1}l''(\Delta^*)$ is bounded in probability. Therefore, the proof is complete. \square

In the next theorem and definition, we show that the proposed pairwise likelihood method is equivalent to Rao's score type test.

Theorem 3.3. *Assume that the regularity conditions and Theorem 3.2 hold. Under the null hypothesis, $H_0 : \Delta = \Delta_0$,*

$$R_n^2 \xrightarrow{D} \chi^2(1)$$

where the test statistic $R_n^2 = (\frac{l'(\Delta_0)}{\sqrt{nI(\Delta_0)}})^2$ and χ_1^2 is the Chi-Square random variable with degrees of freedom of 1.

Proof. By the central limit theorem and $I(\Delta) = \text{Var}(\frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta} \log[u(Y - X - \Delta)]) < \infty$, we can write that

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}l'(\Delta_0) = \sqrt{n} \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^{n_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta} \log[u(y_j - x_i - \Delta)] \right) \xrightarrow{D} N[0, I(\Delta_0)]$$

where $n = n_1 n_2$. From the fundamental theorems of mathematical statistics, we know that the square of a standard normal random variable is a chi square with degrees of freedom of 1. Thus, we have

$$(3.1) \quad R_n = \frac{l'(\Delta_0)}{\sqrt{nI(\Delta_0)}} \xrightarrow{D} N(0, 1)$$

and

$$(3.2) \quad R_n^2 = \left(\frac{l'(\Delta_0)}{\sqrt{nI(\Delta_0)}} \right)^2 \xrightarrow{D} \chi^2(1)$$

Theorem 3.3 also proves that the pairwise likelihood approach is equivalent to the Rao's score type test at the asymptotic level. \square

In the following definition, an asymptotic α level hypothesis test for the pairwise likelihood approach has been defined.

Definition 3.4. *Let Z_{ij} be the pairwise difference of $Y_j - X_i$ for all i and j . Z_{ij} are independent and identically distributed with distribution function $P(Z_{ij} \leq x) = H_\Delta(z - \Delta)$, where $h(z, \Delta) = H'_\Delta(z)$ exists. Also assume that $\text{Var}(Z_{ij}) = \sigma_z^2$. Then, an asymptotic α level test for, $H_0 : \Delta = \Delta_0$ vs $H_a : \Delta \neq \Delta_0$, is any test that rejects H_0 in favor of H_a when $|R_n| \geq z_{\alpha/2}$ where $R_n = \frac{(\bar{Z}_n - \Delta_0)}{\sigma_z/\sqrt{n}}$ and $z_{\alpha/2}$ is the critical value.*

It can be shown that likelihood ratio, Wald and Rao's score type tests are all asymptotically equivalent tests under H_0 . Therefore, all three tests must reach the same decision with probability approaching 1 as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

4. EXAMPLES

Several examples will be provided in this section. Different population distributions result an estimator in different classes such as Normal distribution assumption results an estimator which is similar to the least square estimator, on the other hand, Laplace distribution assumption results Hodges-Lehmann type estimator.

4.1. Example #1. This example will demonstrate the proposed solution under the normality of the random samples assumption. Assume that X_1, \dots, X_{n_1} and Y_1, \dots, Y_{n_2} are two independent iid samples from $N(\mu_x, \sigma^2)$ and $N(\mu_y, \sigma^2)$ distributions, respectively. Define $H_0 : \Delta = \Delta_0$, where $\Delta = \mu_y - \mu_x$. Let $Z_{ij} = Y_j - X_i$ be the pairwise differences. By the equation (2.3), we have

$$(4.1) \quad h(z, \Delta) = \int f(x + z - \Delta) f(x) dx$$

By the normality assumption, $f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp^{-[(x)^2/2]}$, where we also assume that $\mu_x = 0$ and $\sigma^2 = 1$ to simplify the process. If we plug in $f(x)$ into $h(z, \Delta)$,

$$(4.2) \quad \begin{aligned} h(z, \Delta) &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp^{-[(x+z-\Delta)^2/2]} * \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp^{-[(x)^2/2]} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \exp^{-[(x+z-\Delta)^2 - x^2]/2} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \exp^{-(z-\Delta)^2/4} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \exp^{-[x+(z-\Delta)/2]^2} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \exp^{-(z-\Delta)^2/4} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\sqrt{\pi}} \exp^{-[x+(z-\Delta)/2]^2} dx \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2\pi} \exp^{-(z-\Delta)^2/4} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \exp^{-[x+(z-\Delta)/2]^2/(2*1/2)} dx. \end{aligned}$$

The integral inside the function is a normal pdf with $\mu = \frac{\Delta-z}{2}$ and $\sigma^2 = 1/2$. Therefore, by integrating it from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$, we get 1. The term in front of the integral is

$$(4.3) \quad h(z, \Delta) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi}} \exp^{-(z-\Delta)^2/4}, \quad z \in (-\infty, +\infty).$$

which is a normal pdf with $\mu_z = \Delta$ and $\sigma_z^2 = 2$. If $f(x)$ is normal pdf with $\mu_x = 0$ and σ^2 , then $h(z, \Delta)$ will have a normal pdf with $\mu_z = \Delta$ and $\sigma_z^2 = 2\sigma^2$.

We set $h(z, \Delta) = u(z - \Delta)$ as defined by the equation (2.3) which assumes that we have a location model and the parameter is Δ . By the equation (2.4), we will have,

$$l'(\Delta) = - \sum_i^{n_1} \sum_j^{n_2} \left(\frac{z_{ij} - \Delta}{\sigma_z^2} \right)$$

We set $l'(\Delta) = 0$ and solve for Δ . It is not difficult to see that the estimator is $\hat{\Delta} = \bar{Y} - \bar{X}$. In fact, this is known as the least square estimator of shift parameter in the literature. Moreover, Rao's score type test can be developed by the result of

the Theorem 3.3:

$$(4.4) \quad R_n^2 = \left(\frac{l'(\Delta_0)}{\sqrt{nI(\Delta_0)}} \right)^2$$

We first find the likelihood function, $L(\Delta)$, of the paired differences.

$$\begin{aligned} L(\Delta) &= \prod_i^{n_1} \prod_j^{n_2} u(z_{ij} - \Delta) \\ &= \prod_i^{n_1} \prod_j^{n_2} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_z}} \right) e^{-\sum_i^{n_1} \sum_j^{n_2} \frac{(z_{ij} - \Delta)^2}{2\sigma_z^2}} \end{aligned}$$

By adding and subtracting \bar{z} inside the exponential term, and working it out, we get,

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_z^2} \right)^{n_1 n_2 / 2} e^{-\sum_i^{n_1} \sum_j^{n_2} \frac{(z_i - \bar{z} + \bar{z} + \Delta)^2}{2\sigma_z^2}} \\ (4.5) \quad &= \left(\frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_z^2} \right)^{n_1 n_2 / 2} e^{-\sum_i^{n_1} \sum_j^{n_2} \frac{(z_{ij} - \bar{z})^2}{\sigma_z^2}} e^{-\sum_i^{n_1} \sum_j^{n_2} \frac{(\bar{z} - \Delta)^2}{\sigma_z^2}} \end{aligned}$$

By setting $n = n_1 n_2$, taking the log of both sides and derivative with respect to Δ , we find that

$$\begin{aligned} (4.6) \quad l'(\Delta) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta} \log[L(\Delta)] = \frac{(\bar{z} - \Delta)}{\sigma_z^2 / n} \\ \frac{\sigma_z}{\sqrt{n}} l'(\Delta) &= \frac{(\bar{z} - \Delta)}{\sigma_z / \sqrt{n}} \end{aligned}$$

By taking the square of the above result, we have

$$(4.7) \quad \left[\frac{\sigma_z}{\sqrt{n}} l'(\Delta) \right]^2 = \left(\frac{\bar{z} - \Delta}{\sigma_z / \sqrt{n}} \right)^2$$

We define a test statistic $R_n^2 = \left(\frac{l'(\Delta_0)}{\sqrt{nI(\Delta_0)}} \right)^2$ where $I(\Delta_0) = \frac{1}{\sigma_z^2}$ which is the Fisher Information. The right side of the equation is z^2 and has a $\chi^2(1)$ under H_0 . This is similar to Rao's score type test statistics and proven by the Theorem 3.3. If we use the equation (4.7) above, an α level test based on Normal Distribution model example can be developed as

To test hypothesis of $H_0 : \Delta = \Delta_0$ vs $H_1 : \Delta \neq \Delta_0$, we use the test statistics:

$$R_n^2 = \left(\frac{\bar{z} - \Delta_0}{\sigma_z / \sqrt{n}} \right)^2 \rightarrow \chi^2(1)$$

A decision rule for a size α test is to reject H_0 if $R_n^2 \geq \chi_\alpha^2(1)$.

4.2. Example #2. In this example, we will demonstrate the proposed estimator under the assumption that $F(x)$ is an exponential distribution with λ parameter. First, we assume that X_1, \dots, X_{n_1} and Y_1, \dots, Y_{n_2} are two independent iid samples from $F(x)$ and $G(x)$, respectively. Define $H_0 : \Delta = \Delta_0$, where $\Delta = \mu_y - \mu_x$. Let $Z_{ij} = Y_j - X_i$ be the pairwise differences. By the equation (2.3), we have

$$(4.8) \quad h(z, \Delta) = \int f(x + z - \Delta) f(x) dx$$

By the assumption that $F(x)$ has an exponential distribution with λ , we have $f(x) = \frac{1}{\lambda} \exp^{-x/\lambda}$ for $x > 0$. If we plug in $f(x)$ into $h(z, \Delta)$ and if $z - \Delta > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned}
(4.9) \quad h(z, \Delta) &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\lambda} \exp^{-(x+z-\Delta)/\lambda} * \frac{1}{\lambda} \exp^{-x/\lambda} dx \\
&= \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \exp^{-(x+z-\Delta)/\lambda - x/\lambda} dx \\
&= \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \int_0^{+\infty} \exp^{-(x+z-\Delta-x)/\lambda} dx \\
&= \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \exp^{-(z-\Delta)/\lambda} \int_0^{+\infty} \exp^{-(2x)/\lambda} dx \\
&= \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \exp^{-(z-\Delta)/\lambda} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{\lambda/2}{\lambda/2} \exp^{-x/\lambda/2} dx \\
&= \frac{\lambda/2}{\lambda^2} \exp^{-(z-\Delta)/\lambda} \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\lambda/2} \exp^{-x/\lambda/2} dx
\end{aligned}$$

The integral part of the function inside is an exponential pdf with $\lambda/2$, therefore, the integrating it from 0 to $+\infty$ gives us 1. The term in front of the integral is

$$(4.10) \quad h(z, \Delta) = \frac{1}{2\lambda} \exp^{-(z-\Delta)/\lambda}, \quad z - \Delta > 0.$$

If we assume $z - \Delta < 0$, and applying the similar approach as above, we get

$$(4.11) \quad h(z, \Delta) = \frac{1}{2\lambda} \exp^{-(\Delta-z)/\lambda}, \quad z - \Delta < 0.$$

Therefore,

$$(4.12) \quad h_{\Delta}(z) = \frac{1}{2\lambda} e^{-|z-\Delta|/\lambda}, \quad -\infty < z < \infty.$$

which is a Laplace distribution with $\mu_z = \Delta$ and $\sigma_z^2 = \lambda$. Define $H_0 : \Delta = \Delta_0$. The likelihood function is

$$(4.13) \quad L(\Delta) = (2\lambda)^{-n} e^{-\sum_i^{n_1} \sum_j^{n_2} |y_j - x_i - \Delta|/\lambda}$$

The score function is

$$(4.14) \quad l'(\Delta) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \Delta} \log[L(\Delta)] = \sum_i^{n_1} \sum_j^{n_2} \text{sign}(y_j - x_i - \Delta)/\lambda$$

We set this result to "zero" and solve for Δ . We find that $\hat{\Delta} = \text{median}\{y_j - x_i\}$ which is equivalent to the Hodges-Lehmann estimator of Δ .

An asymptotic α level test based on Laplace distribution model example can be developed as well. To test hypothesis of $H_0 : \Delta = \Delta_0$ vs $H_1 : \Delta \neq \Delta_0$, we use the test statistics:

$$R_n^2 = \left(\frac{l'(\Delta_0)}{\sqrt{nI(\Delta_0)}} \right)^2 = (S)^2/n \rightarrow \chi_{\alpha}^2(1)$$

where Fisher information, $I(\Delta_0) = \lambda$ and $S = \sum_i^{n_1} \sum_j^{n_2} \text{sign}(y_j - x_i - \Delta_0)$

A decision rule for a size α test is to reject H_0 if $R_n^2 \geq \chi^2(1)$.

5. CONCLUSION

We showed that by using the pairwise differences of two random samples, an estimator of shift parameter, Δ , can be estimated. The proposed method uses $Z_{ij} = Y_j - X_i$ differences and assumes that Z_{ij} has a pdf of $h(z; \Delta)$, where Δ is the location parameter. The theory of the method is similar to the typical maximum likelihood theorems and conditions. An estimator of the shift, $\hat{\Delta}$, can be found by Newton's one step estimator if there is no explicit result found for the estimator. In fact, R algorithm for this estimator is provided in the appendix. Asymptotic properties of the estimator are shown in section 3. It has been shown that an estimator from the pairwise differences has asymptotic normality under some regularity conditions. An asymptotic level score test (Rao's score test) is also developed for the estimator. Moreover, in section 4, two examples which are provided in the study show that under the normality of $F(x)$, the resulting estimator is equal to the least squares estimator, $\hat{\Delta} = \bar{Y} - \bar{X}$ and under the assumption of exponential distribution of $F(x)$, the resulting estimator is equal to Hodges-Lehmann estimator, $\hat{\Delta} = \text{Median}\{Y_j - X_i\}$. One of the main advantages of using pairwise differences is to estimate the shift parameter with only one known distribution function, $F(x)$, instead of two. As a result, using pairwise differences of the two samples, a pdf of $h(z, \Delta)$ for the differences can be found. Also assuming Δ as a location parameter, two sample location problem can be treated as one sample location problem and $\hat{\Delta}$ can be found by maximizing the log likelihood function of $h(z, \Delta)$.

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6. APPENDIX

This section contains R algorithms used in the estimation of shift parameter and pdf of $h(z, \Delta)$. These algorithms can also be reached from Tasdan [7].

```
plog<-function(t,x,y){
n1<-length(x)
n2<-length(y)
n<-n1*n2
sig<-spool(x,y)
a<-outer(y,x,"-")
da <- c(a[row(a) <= col(a)])
```

```

db <- c(a[row(a) > col(a)])
dab <- append(da, db)
b<-rep(0,n)
for(i in 1:n){
b[i]<-log(f1(dab[i],x,dab,t))
}
l<--sum(b)
l
}

```

Convolution function to find $h(z, \Delta)$:

```

f1<-function(z,dab,t){
  sig<-mad(dab) # robust estimate of deviation by MAD function
  m<-mean(dab)
  #a<-integrate(function(x) {dnorm((x+z-t),0,sig)*dnorm(x,0,sig)}, -Inf, Inf)$value
  if((z-t)>0){a<-integrate(function(x) {dexp((x+z-t),m)*dexp(x,m)}, 0, Inf)$value}
  else{a<-integrate(function(x) {dexp((x-(z-t)),m)*dexp(x,m)}, 0, Inf)$value}
  #a<-integrate(function(x) {dcauchy((x+z-t),0,sig)*dcauchy(x,0,sig)}, -Inf, Inf)$value
  #a<-integrate(function(x) {dlaplace((x+z-t),0,1/m)*dlaplace(x,0,1/m)}, 0, Inf)$value
  #a<-integrate(function(x) {dfun((x+z-t)/sig)*dfun(x/sig)}, 0, Inf)$value
  #a<-integrate(function(x) {dunif((x+z-t),0,1)*dunif(x,0,1)}, -Inf, Inf)$value
  a
}

```

Minimization of log likelihood to estimate the shift parameter. The function uses plog function from above:

```

finder<-function(x, y)
{
# Estimating Shift parameter by using nlm(nonlinear minimization) function in R
# function "plog" has to be used here
n1 <- length(x)
n2 <- length(y)
n <- n1 + n2
options(warn=-1)
d1<-nlm(plog,0,x=x,y=y)
d2 <- round(d1$estimate, 7)
d2
}

```

Newton's one step estimator:

```

finder1<-function(x,y,tol,dl,du){# finding shift parameter via
                                #Newton's one step...
n<-length(x)
m<-length(y)
change<-100
step<-0
dold<-du
while(change>tol&&step<50){
s1<-plog(x,y,dl) #plog is required function
s2<-plog(x,y,du)

```

```
d<-dl-((s1*(du-dl))/(s2-s1))
change<-abs((d-dold)/d)
if(change<tol){
break
}
else{dold<-d
s3<-plog(x,y,d)
if((s1*s3)>0){
dl<-d
}
else{du<-d
}
}
step<-step+1
cat("step=",step,"Est=",round(d,4),"\n")
}
d
}
```

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